

Explainable Artificial Intelligence Based Early-Stage Detection of Liver Cancer

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Abstract - In human anatomy, the liver has a special feature called regeneration, and this feature helps the liver to grow back even after a large part of its organ is removed. Like regeneration, it helps maintain bile salts, protein synthesis, and detoxification. Irregular eating habits, sleep, and alcohol consumption increase liver function and cause various diseases such as fatty liver and other liver problems. Hepatocellular carcinoma is one of the liver diseases, and it is caused by the abnormal growth of cells in the liver. In such cases, liver regeneration is possible if the disease is identified at an early stage. To support this early identification, several research works have been carried out using both artificial intelligence and deep learning techniques. Therefore, this paper proposed an automated approach to identify liver cancer at an early stage through a segmentation and classification using deep learning techniques. The early-stage identification becomes possible with the dual stage of segmentation using U-NET and XAI. The U-NET helps to segment the image through its various texture properties of the image. Then, the XAI is used to analyze the individual regions of the image. This special feature of this approach is that it uses descriptive AI for classification, and this helps in identifying critical regions through heat maps and saliency maps. This technique was tested on a computed tomography dataset of liver images and its performance was evaluated in terms of precision, accuracy, recall and F1-score.

Keywords - Liver Cancer, Deep Learning, Segmentation, Classification, U-NET, Explainable AI.

INTRODUCTION

In human anatomy, the liver has a special feature called regeneration, and the regenerative property helps it grow back even after a large part of the liver is removed. Like regeneration, it helps maintain bile salts, protein synthesis, and detoxification. Irregular eating habits, sleep, and alcohol consumption increase liver function and cause various diseases such as fatty liver and other liver problems. Hepatocellular carcinoma is one of the liver diseases, and it is caused by the abnormal growth of cells in the liver. In such cases, liver regeneration is possible if the disease is identified at an early stage. To support this early identification, several research works have been carried out using both artificial intelligence and deep learning techniques. A PRISMA based flow chart analysis was proposed in [1] to analyze the Convolution Neural Network (CNN) functionalities in lesion segmentation and classification of Liver Computed Tomography (CT) images. It utilized the medical databases and medical based journals for analysis and the results showed that the Deep Learning techniques like CNN are performing well in lesion segmentation and classification effectively. Like DL, the hand craft features role in cancer classification was studied in [2]. Both these [1] and [2] give an insight about the DL and hand craft features role in cancer classification. A multi-stage Deep learning technique was used in [3] and [4] for liver tumor

segmentation. Instead of attention and multi-stages, the General Adversarial Network (GAN) was used in [5] and it achieved better dice score value of 97%. A generalized CNN was proposed in [6] for segmenting the liver tumors in MRI and CT images. The common features in [3], [4] and [5] are that the U-net was used for segmentation and in [7] the U-net was enhanced as Un network for segmentation. Like [4], in [8] also a multiple stage segmentation was proposed for liver segmentation using U-Net, Fuzzy C-means and Level set segmentation algorithms. A multi-stage with input image variation and U-Net is used for liver tumor segmentation [9]. In [10], the Artificial bee colony algorithm was combined with Segnet- U-net to tune its hyper parameter and in Lenet ABC is used for selecting topology models. Both networks performed well in different aspects of Liver tumor segmentation.

The combination of U-net and Residual networks was used for liver and lesion segmentation in [11]. While in [12], the U-net was combined with GAN for lesion segmentation of liver. The attention mechanism was added to the U-net in [13] to perform liver and tumor segmentation on arterial and venous phase liver images. The U-net based segmentation technique achieved Dice Score value between 53% to 95%. Instead of U-net, in [14] the grey level co-occurrence matrix-based features and enhanced loss function is used in the Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification, and it achieved classification accuracy of 98.9%. Like U-Net, [15] proposed an encoder and

decoder structure using deformable Convolution networks, which constructed using atrous spatial pyramid pooling layers for liver segmentation and it achieved around 95% as DSC value. Like GAN, in [16], a couinaud segmentation network is proposed which utilizes both tumor and healthy image pixel intensities for two stage training-based classification. In [17], the Hyper spectral image of liver region is used for segmentation and classification using U-Net and Explainable AI.

The XAI helps to improve its classification accuracy to 93% using features from 224 bands. In [18], the U-net was enhanced with attention mechanisms, and it helped to achieve 77% DSC value in testing set of Lits dataset. Even though DL performed well in segmentation and classification, it required larger datasets and tuned hyper parameters for better performance. While in [19], showed that selected hand-crafted features and proper classifier can also identify tumor effectively. Apart from DL techniques perspective, the article [20] highlighted the publicly available liver datasets, techniques used for liver and lesion segmentation. In [21], the image-to-image translation technique proposed for liver tumor segmentation. The pre-trained DL models were combined to form a hybrid DL model for tumor classification task and this hybrid DL achieved 99% accuracy in classification task [22]. A modified encoder-decoder architecture is proposed in [23] with CNN for liver tumor segmentation and classification is proposed. In [24] also the U-Net performance is enhanced using large skip network connections and different loss functions to enhance its liver segmentation process. Like [24], the articles [25], [26] and [27] enhanced the U-network for improving segmentation using attention unit or parallel units. As classifiers were only modified in Liver classification, it can be enhanced through a new technique called Explainable AI. The article [29] and [30] highlighted the features and XAI role in health care units.

II. RELATED WORKS

Jiang et al., (2019) proposed a hybrid technique based Deep learning network for liver tumor segmentation using 3DIRCADb dataset. Here, they utilized both hard and soft attention mechanisms to highlight the lesion segmentation. Similarly, they used both long and short skip connections to preserve pixel features and remove unnecessary information. Along with hybrid techniques, the dice loss function is used to tune the classification performance, and it achieved 59.1% as dice score value.

Bai et al., (2019) proposed a multi-stage segmentation process for liver tumor segmentation using Lits2017 dataset. In the first

stage, the U-net is used, and it is followed by super pixel-based segmentation using multi-scale candidate. In the third stage, 3D fractal residual network is used for tumor classification, and it is followed by active contour segmentation for better classification. With this multiple stage, it achieved 67% as dice score values.

Xia et al., (2019) also utilized the U-net for segmentation but they utilized the U-net for generation part in General Adversarial Network (GAN) and it followed by discriminator to tune the pixel segmentation. With this Pix2Pix based GAN, it achieved 97% of the dice score value.

Afshar et al., (2020) modified the U-net as Un network for segmenting and classifying the liver and tumor region using Lits and 3DIRCADb dataset. Here, the features from convolution modules were used for segmentation and classification instead of skip connection features. This helps to achieve above 70% in DSC in both datasets.

Li et al., (2020) also utilized the U-net for liver tumor segmentation. But here, they utilized the multiple stages segmentation by varying the input images as follows: first stage and third stage processed the whole input image. While in the second stage, image patches were used for analysis. It achieved 82% DSC value in Lits dataset.

Like U-Net, Li et al., (2021) proposed an encoder and decoder structure using deformable Convolution networks, which constructed using atrous spatial pyramid pooling layers. With this Deformable Encoder-Decoder architecture, it achieved above 95% dice score value in liver segmentation.

Zhang et al., (2021) utilized Multi-Tasking U-net for liver segmentation and Explainable network model for tumor classification using CT and Hyperspectral images. Here, the explainable AI is used to define salient features of tumor from five spectral bands of liver images. This approach achieved DSC value of 92.1% and its accuracy is 93% by using 224 bands.

Hussain et al., (2022) utilized the 55 hand craft features and four classifiers like Random Forest, J48, Decision Tree and logistic network for tumor classification using liver CT images. It utilized the feature selection process to select the best 20 features, and these features were used for classification, and it achieved around 90% accuracy in all classifiers and Random Forest classifier performed well by achieving 95% accuracy.

Napte et al., (2023) proposed a modified U-net using edge strengthening techniques for segmentation and a light weight deep convolutional neural network is used for classification.

This approach achieved better accuracy of 95% with increased DCNN layers.

Contribution of the Paper

The following points highlighted the current Liver segmentation and classification network salient features.

- Most of the network utilized U-net for segmentation. Because U-net specializes in pixel-based segmentation, and it is helpful for lesion segmentation.
- The final tumor classification can be performed through either using hand craft or deep features with tuned hyper parameters.
- In other AI and DL techniques, the critical/highly damaged region is not highlighted.
- To overcome this problem, the following process was taken in this paper:
- Due to U-net special features, this paper utilized the U-net based segmentation for liver region localization.
- XAI helps to highlight the critical region of the liver through its heat map and saliency map.
- This highlighting helps the physician to take preventive measures at the right time to save the lives.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A U-Net based liver region Segmentation and Explainable AI based liver tumor classification is proposed in this work. In practical aspect, the proposed approach processed in an automated way because it utilized deep learning techniques for both segmentation and classification. This helps to The dataflow in the proposed approach is presented in the flow chart in figure.

Fig. 1. Liver Classification using U-net & X-AI

The data flow in UNET-XAI based Liver classification is presented in figure 1. A brief process of this approach is given in the following algorithm 1.

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Algorithm 1: UNET& XAI based Liver classification
Input: Liver Images and its labels
Output: Output Labels and its performance assessment values.
Begin
Load images as image data-stores.
Perform pre-processing using Algorithm 2.
Segment liver region using U-net segmentation
Classify segmented liver region XAI.
Evaluate results
Stop
    
```

Input Liver Dataset

The input images were taken from the openly available public dataset called Nifti dataset. This dataset comprises of CT images with two liver problems; namely abnormal and Normal liver were used for the analysis.

Liver Image Preparation

This process in the proposed approach is to equalize the image dimensionality and remove the artefacts in the image. To perform this, the following steps were performed on the images.

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Algorithm 2: Image Preparation
Input: LS
Output:  $P_{LS}$ 
Begin
Load LS
For all images in LS
Normalize LS using equation 1.
Resize using equation 2
Remove noise using equation 3;
End
Return  $P_{LS}$  (pre-processed output)
End
    
```

Intensity Image Transformation

The input image has three channels called R, G and B and this 3-channel reduced to 1 channel using equation 1.

$$P_{LS} = 0.299 * LS(:, :, R) + 0.587 * LS(:, :, G) + 0.114 * LS(:, :, B)$$

Image Augmentation

To augment the images, the input image is resized to [224,224] using equation 2 and random noise is introduced in image using mean and variance and then it is filtered using Wiener filter using equation 3.

$$P_{LS} = imresize(P_{LS}, [224 224])$$

$$P_{LS} = mean(P_{LS}) + (P_{LS} - mean(P_{LS})) * \left(\frac{Variance(P_{LS})}{Variance(P_{LS}) + Variance(Noise)} \right)$$

U-Net Based Liver Region Segmentation

The first stage of Liver region segmentation is performed through windowing technique. In the second stage, the abnormal region in the liver is extracted through U-net segmentation. Due to its precise and pixel based segmentation, U-net model is highly preferred for medical image segmentation. The U-shaped network consists of two paths and its functionalities are presented in table 1.

Table 1.U-Net paths

Path	Functions	Layers and its purpose	purpose
Contracting Path (Encoder)	Down sample the input data	Convolution and pooling layers	To extract features
Expanding path (Decoder)	Up sample	Skip connections	Segmented output with preserved spatial information

Contracting Path (Encoder)

The encoder extracts complex features from the image through conventional Convolutional Neural Network based down sampling operation.

Here, the CNN blocks are made up of two 3 * 3 Convolutional layers and it is followed by Rectified Linear Unit (RLU) layer and RLU is followed by 2*2 max-pooling layers. The first two layers help to extract the complex features and max-pooling layers minimize the spatial resolution of the feature map. The

Convolutional block operation is presented in the following equation:

$$ConvBlock(PL) = \sigma(W_2 \cdot \sigma(W_1 \cdot PL))$$

Here, W_1 and W_2 are the convolutional kernels and σ is the RLU activation function.

As U-NET architecture is in the form of hierarchy models, it extracts multiple sets of complex features from the image. As the liver region is made up of soft tissues, locating the minor abnormal in the image is difficult. This can be overcome by these different levels of abstract features.

Bottle Neck Layer

The encoders provided a feature with higher depth information and minimal spatial information. But for medical images, spatial information is an important one to find the minor abnormalities in the region. For this purpose, the bottle neck layer is used to provide a deep and abstract feature map.

Expanding Path (Decoder)

Spatial information is an important property for any type of regional segmentation technique. This spatial property is preserved in the U-Net through Decoder. Here, the deconvolutions are performed on the down sampled feature map as follows:

$$UpConv(E) = W_{up} \cdot E$$

Here, the E denotes the down sample feature map from the bottle neck layer and W_up denotes the weights of deconvolution or transposed convolutions.

These up-sampled feature maps and down-sample feature maps were combined through skip connections to preserve spatial information.

Skip Connections

It is an important connection in U-net that helps to preserve the spatial information of the image. Here, the encoder and decoder feature maps were concatenated to provide a final feature map at each level of abstraction.

It helps to retain the pixel or spatial properties of the images that helps to identify the fine boundaries between the normal and abnormal regions of the liver.

Final Layer

The final layer consists of three sub-layers as follows: one 1*1 convolutional layer for segmentation and it's followed by soft max layer and the final layer is pixel classification layer.

The final layer uses a 1x1 convolution to output the binary segmentation mask (in liver segmentation, this would be a mask

distinguishing the liver region from other tissues). The final segmentation of liver is given as follows:

$$f(PL) = \text{softmax}(C(PL))$$

Here, the $f(PL)$ denotes the final segmented output, PL denotes the pre-processed liver image and $C(PL)$ denotes the combined encoder-decoder architectures. With the U-net, the liver region is segmented as background, liver and abnormal region. The performance of U-net can be enhanced by using proper loss functions. The types of loss function in U-net is presented below.

U-Net tuning

The U-net can improve its segmentation results by choosing any one of the following loss functions:

- Dice Loss
- Binary cross Entropy Loss
- Hybrid (DL+BCE)

In this, the hybrid loss is used. Because the BCE loss is used for different classes in the image and is calculated using the following equation.

$$L_{BCE} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_i^c \log(py_i^c)$$

Here, y indicates the true label and py indicates the predicted label. N and C represent the number of pixels and number of classes in the image. Similarly, the dice coefficient loss is calculated using the following equation.

$$L_D = 1 - \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|}$$

This loss helps to minimize the overlap between the original and predicted segmentation maps. Here A denotes the predicted map, and B denotes the original maps.

As the proposed work involves multiple classes and fine boundaries between regions, the hybrid loss is used for tuning. Apart from this, the U-net performance can be enhanced by adjusting the Batch Size and Learning Rate. For better performance both these values should be selected as lower in this work, as it segments only three regions of the liver. This lower rate also ensures a stable change in training.

Post-processing

Post-processing is required after U-net segmentation to refine the boundaries of the segmented region. Mostly, this post-processing step involves any one of the following processes in table 2.

Table 2. Post Processing

Type	Function	Purpose
Threshold	Binary image formation with specific threshold	For crisp boundaries
Morphological operations	Opening or closing operation	For smooth boundaries
Connected component analysis	Nearest neighbor algorithms	To remove false regions or noise in the mask

In this, the morphological and connected component analysis is used for post-processing. This helps to refine the boundaries in the final mask.

Explainable AI for tumor classification

The explainable AI performs classification using two modules as follows:

- DL module for classification.
- Explainable modules for highlighting the critical regions.

Classification DL module

In this, the traditional RESNET 50 architecture was used for the classification. The transfer learning [30] technique is applied on the pre-trained RESNET 50 feature layer and is replaced with the liver image feature layer for classifying the liver regions as cancer or non-cancerous region. The output of this module is as follows:

$$O_{cl} = W_L \cdot \sigma(W_{L-1} \cdot \sigma(W_1 \cdot \sigma))$$

Explainable Techniques

The XAI technique is mainly used to highlight the tumor and non-tumor regions thoroughly by using three processes as presented in table 3.

Table 3. XAI technique and its Purpose

Technique	Process	Purpose
Grad-CAM	Heat map generation	To highlight tumor and non-tumor regions
LIME	Perturbed Image	Highlight tumor region

SHAP	Statistical calculation	To highlight best feature for tumor classification
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Grad-CAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping)

It advances the tumor classification using heat maps that separate the tumor and non-tumor region through different colors as shown in the figure. Equation 9 is used for Grad-CAM implementation.

$$\alpha_k^c = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial y^c}{\partial A_{ij}^k}$$

Here, Z is the normalization constant and A_{ij}^k is the spatial activation function of the feature map. The term α_k^c is feature map importance of class c. The sample heat map for classifying the tumor and non-tumor region is shown in the below figure.

Fig. 2. Grad-CAM

Here, the non-tumor regions were highlighted in the other colors while the tumor regions were highlighted in the yellow color in the above Grad-CAM image.

Lime

LIME property is to observe the classifier performance for the perturbed image. Here, it uses a linear model to differentiate the original image and perturbed image classification performance. This linear model highlighted the tumor region features as shown in the figure.

Fig. 3. LIME

This LIME image is obtained by the following equation 10.

$$\arg \min_{g \in G} \sum_{z \in Z} \pi_{LS}(z) (f(z) - g(z))^2 + \Omega(z)$$

Here, the z is the perturbed image and f is the model prediction value and g is the proximity value and Ω is the complex penalty.

Shap

SHAP property is used to highlight the pixel features that are highly used for tumor classification. Here, S is the feature subset, and N is the total features and ϕ is the SHAP feature values.

$$\phi = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! (|N| - |S| - 1)!}{|N|!} [f(S \cup \{i\}) - f(S)]$$

The final classification region is obtained by overlapping the Grad-CAM heat map on liver region to classify the tumor and non-tumor region using following equation.

$$L_{Grad} = RELU \left(\sum \alpha_k^c A^k \right)$$

Fig. 4. SHAP image

Evaluation Metrics

The proposed method performance is evaluated in terms of the confusion matrix as shown in the figure.

Classes	Tumor	Non-Tumor
Tumor	TP	FN
Non-Tumor	FP	TN

Fig. 5. Binary Classification Confusion Matrix

The letters T, F, P and N denote the true, false, positive and negative. TP means true positive that indicates the liver tumor is identified correctly. While FN means False Negative that indicates the liver tumor is identified incorrectly as non-tumor. Similarly, TN and FP means True Negative and False Positive and its vice versa of TP and FN. This confusion matrix is helpful for calculating the following evaluation metrics:

Table 4. Performance Assessment Metrics

Metrics	Purpose	Equations (13-16)
Accuracy	It verifies the classifier performance on identifying TP and TN	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$
Precision	It evaluates the TP performance	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$

Recall	It is to identify the correctly identified TP	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
F1-score	To balance both precision and recall i.e. identification of TP and TN	$\frac{2 * Recall * Precision}{Recall + precision}$

With these values, the proposed technique performance was analyzed for the testing set. In general, the metric values must be high for better classifier performance.

The deep spatial features from liver images were extracted through RN-50.

Results And Discussion

A google Colab Notebook is used for realizing the proposed U-NET& XAI based Liver tumor classification in CPU environment.

The raw nifii image of abdomen region is shown in the below figure.

Fig. 6. Input image

The above figure is the scanned image that includes all parts like liver, pancreas, spleen and other parts in the abdomen region.

From this image, the liver part is extracted through the windowing technique. From the windowed image, the liver region is extracted through U-NET based segmentation. The corresponding outputs of the U-net segmentation is shown in the below figures.

Fig. 7. Pre-processed Final Output

After obtaining the liver region from U-NET, it is subjected to the RESNET-50 for final classification. The final feature layer of the liver dataset is shown in the below figures.

From Resnet-50 and XAI, the tumor and non-tumor region is highlighted as shown in the below figures. It can be seen that in Resnet-50 feature maps, the tumor regions were not highlighted. With the help of XAI methods, the tumor regions were highlighted as explained in XAI module. This helps to segment the tumor and non-tumor regions effectively.

Fig. 8. U-Net based Liver segmentation

The proposed method performance was assessed in terms of XAI classification and its evaluation metrics. As most of the existing works utilized the U-NET for segmentation and it achieved higher DSC values in all U-NET models. But the classification module had issues with proper identification. Hence, this paper utilized XAI features to highlight the tumor regions effectively and its performance is presented in the below table 5.

Table 5. Overall Performance Analysis

Metrics Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
DCNN (2 Layers)	87.10	88	86	87
DCNN (3 Layers)	92.9	94	91	92
U-NET XAI	93.61	94.2	95.2	94.8

It can be seen from table 1 and the confusion matrices of XAI classification, the deep features based XAI classification performed well as compared to other feature sets.

Fig. 9. Accuracy Comparison

Fig. 10. Precision Comparison

Fig. 11. Recall Comparison

Fig. 12. F1-score Comparison

From the table and above figures, the DCNN and XAI performed well in tumor classification. While in DCNN, the number of layers determine the classifier performance. But in the proposed XAI, the tumor region feature is responsible for classification using Grad-CAM map. Apart from this, the XAI precision, recall and F1-score values are higher than the DCNN. It is achieved through LIME and SHAP features. Both LIME and SHAP helps to identify and highlight the tumor region feature effectively than other techniques.

This shows that the XAI performs well than the DCNN for liver tumor classification.

Discussion

As the proposed technique utilized XAI to highlight the tumor region effectively than other classifiers. Its classification accuracy is highlighted in the below table.

Table 6. Performance Comparison

Technique	Accuracy (%)
DCNN [2 layers] [25]	87.10
DCNN [3 layers] [25]	92
DCNN [25]	88
Pre-processed DCNN [25]	92
Proposed U-NET XAI	93.6

In [25] also, the U-net is used for segmentation and lightweight DCNN is used for classification and its performance metrics showed that it performed well in classification. But in the proposed XAI, the classification performance is improved with 1.6% and it highlights the features of tumor regions effectively than DCNN.

With this, the XAI is best for tumor region classification in segmented liver regions.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed approach utilized the U-net for liver segmentation and XAI for classification. The proposed XAI highlighted the tumor region feature is responsible for classification using Grad-CAM map. Apart from this, the XAI precision, recall and F1-score values are higher than the DCNN. It is achieved through LIME and SHAP features. Both LIME and SHAP help to identify and highlight the tumor region feature effectively than other techniques. With these properties, the XAI technique outperformed the existing DCNN in terms of tumor classification.

Future Work

In future, the XAI can implement multi-modal images to highlight the tumor regions effectively.

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